

SPECIFICITY OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN LANGUAGE LESSONS

Usmonova Mehriniso Umarovna

Teacher of Termez State University

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Abstract. Today, the younger generation is increasingly interested in learning foreign languages. Therefore, the teaching of foreign languages, including English, in secondary schools requires the use of interactive methods in the classroom. This article focuses on the effectiveness of organizing lessons using interactive methods in English classes in secondary schools.

Keywords: method, interactive method, information and communication technologies, interactivity.

СПЕЦИФИКА ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ НА УРОКАХ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

Аннотация. Сегодня молодое поколение все больше интересуется изучением иностранных языков. Поэтому преподавание иностранных языков, в том числе английского, в общеобразовательных школах требует использования интерактивных методов на занятиях. В данной статье речь пойдет об эффективности организации уроков с использованием интерактивных методов на уроках английского языка в общеобразовательных школах.

Ключевые слова: метод, интерактивный метод, информационно-коммуникационные технологии, интерактивность.

INTRODUCTION

Significant work is being done in our country to form an information society, to introduce the most advanced information and communication technologies in all areas. In particular, the capabilities of interactive services in this process are highly valued. The Uzbek dictionary defines the term "interactive" as based on the reception or transmission of information over a computer network. Wikipedia, on the other hand, evaluates interactivity as a concept that reveals the nature and extent of interactions between objects and is said to be used in information theory, computer science and programming, telecommunications systems, sociology, industrial design, and more. In short, interactivity is a system of organizing a system to achieve a specific goal by facilitating the exchange of information between parts of the system. The interactive method serves to stimulate the acquisition of knowledge by students, the development of personal qualities by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process. The use of interactive methods helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The main criteria for interactive education are: informal discussions, the ability to freely express and express the learning material, a small number of lectures, but a large number of seminars, opportunities for students to take the initiative, small group, large group, assignment to work as a class team, written work and other methods, which have a special role in increasing the effectiveness of educational work. One of the main directions in improving teaching methods today is the introduction of interactive teaching and learning methods. All science teachers are increasingly using interactive methods in their teaching. As a result of using interactive methods, students develop the skills of independent thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, expressing their opinions, defending them on the basis of them, healthy communication, discussion, debate. In the process of interactive learning, the lesson is based on the interaction of students. Derived

from the English word "interactive", "Interact" means "interaction", "act" - means action, influence, activity. Interactivity is the interaction of two people, that is, the learning process takes place in the form of a conversation, in the form of dialogue (computer communication) or on the basis of teacher-student interaction. Interactivity - interaction, movement, sensitivity, occurs in student-teacher, student-student (subject-subject) conversations. The main purpose of interactive methods is to create the most favorable environment for the shooting process, creating an environment for active, free, creative thinking of the student, the use of his needs, interests, inner potential. Such lessons take place in such a way that in the process, no student is left out, and has the opportunity to openly express their views on what they have heard, read and seen. There is a process of mutual exchange of views. Children develop an interest in learning, and friendly relations are formed. Modern interactive methods in foreign language teaching methods have been developed by scientists and have been proven to be more effective than traditional methods. Interactive methods significantly increase the knowledge potential of the learning process compared to traditional methods. Because in interactive methods, the student thinks independently and works in partnership with the teacher. When teaching a foreign language using modern technologies, the student plans the lesson process, engages in it on the basis of the curriculum, chooses teaching methods jointly by the student and the teacher, o ' participate in the discussion of the study material. Students help each other.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, the term "interactive" methods in education was widely used in the pedagogical literature. We will try to explain the meaning of this phrase. "Inter" is used in the extreme sense. Interactive means a very active learning method. This group of methods allows students to think independently, be creative, and be interested in the content of the topic. It is more effective than traditional methods of teaching, such as interactive teaching methods, explanation, demonstration and use of tools, which is an important factor in shaping students as individuals, developing their personal abilities, ensuring their creative independence.

Interactive learning technology - ensures that every teacher conducts the lessons that all students learn as intended. In this case, each student, with their own motives and intellectual level, masters the lesson at the intended level. Based on the study of some experiences in the practical application of interactive training, we can identify some of the factors that affect the quality and effectiveness of these trainings. They can be conditionally called organizational-pedagogical, scientific-methodical and factors related to the teacher, students, teaching aids. We need to keep in mind that they have a positive or negative effect, depending on their nature. There are many types of interactive activities, which are selected and prepared according to the nature of the subject and the objectives. There are specific requirements for the preparation of students to participate in interactive lessons, which include the acquisition of knowledge necessary for active participation in the lesson, readiness for communication, collaboration, independent thinking, self-expression.

RESULTS

Skills of free expression and defense, and so on. Making the most of your time is a must. This requires the correct selection and preparation of the necessary tools, as well as a clear definition of the trainers and their responsibilities. There are specific differences between interactive methods and traditional teaching methods, and each teacher should compare these

differences, their advantages and disadvantages in relation to each other, in choosing the methods of lesson planning and conduct should be taken into account. In this case, the most appropriate interactive for the transfer of new knowledge, the formation, development, strengthening of skills, repetition of knowledge, practical training, as well as for training on each topic, taking into account the specifics of the subject or the correct choice of other techniques. The application of properly selected techniques will ensure that the training is fun and effective.

Therefore, there is a growing attempt to use interactive teaching methods in the educational process, which do not teach the student, but teach him to read and learn. In short, a teacher who aims to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson will achieve his or her goal only if he or she skillfully uses interactive teaching methods in their place. Today foreign language as a subject is increasingly becoming a language for the profession and is intended to ensure the readiness of future specialists for adaptation and self-determination in the world of new information technologies, for long-life education and personal development. Foreign language is an organic component of such training. The knowledge of it broadens the professional context of specialists, makes their professional field wider due to availability of foreign information. Social order is expressed in the prestige of the knowledge of a foreign language, in the students' priorities, thereby activating the pragmatic aspects of foreign language learning.

DISCUSSION

The pragmatic approach to the study of foreign languages turns the researchers to Hutchinson and Waters's theory, which focuses on the following conceptual principles of language learning for specific purposes:

- determination of learning objective becomes a constitutive factor in the process of profession-oriented foreign language learning. T. Hutchinson said: «Tell me, why you need English and I'll tell you what English you need»;
- analysis of the learners' needs is a starting point in the construction of profession-oriented courses of training the language of profession;
- language variations and registers become the basis for the language of specific context since the analysis of linguistic characteristics of particular professional areas has revealed no significant differences between the language for special purposes and the basic language;
- language for special purposes is described as a «limited language» used in the situations of professional communication, around which a special vocation-oriented course is constructed [3].

Communicative needs of the profession in turn necessitate the mastering of the communicative competence. Communicative competence as a pedagogical category is characterized by such features as: deep professional knowledge of the individual for successful professional activity, awareness of the personal meanings and values of professional knowledge for the practical and professional activities; awareness of the algorithm for the solution of professional problems, creative approach to any sort of activity, manifestation of tolerance in situations of professional communication [5].

It is obvious that the professional level of communicative competence makes an individual a highly developed personality, improves their social mobility and economic freedom, allows them to enter an open information space [2].

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, in line with mentioned above communicative competence of university students is considered by us as the formation of an integrated personality of system organization and complex structure and having a set of intercultural, linguistic and didactic, discourse, and interpersonal communication skills and knowledge, which are based on the concept of the development of a linguistic personality capable of productive communication, ready for the dialogue. At the stage of communicative communication, the class community is quick to interact to be able to thoroughly understand the techniques of engaging conversation, to be able to respond to all their interests, to be able to freely express their views and the application of various methods of positive influence on the minds of students techniques should be mastered. At the stage of the pedagogical process, the teacher's activities are directly education is the transfer of educational work in a certain direction, students support the initiative, the official and informal of the class community establish a fair dialogue with leaders. Communication in pedagogy teacher and the team of students its essence, mutual Informatics, representing the qualifications, method and system of influence in change, educational and educational interaction, interaction between each other it is manifested in their achievement of understanding and the following: has features;

- * communication is the most important profession in the pedagogical activity of the teacher the weapon is;

- * to carry out its intended implementation in the process of Capricorn social control and social legalities are important to ensure; the most important component of teacher and student relationship what role does Motivation play in part communication, it plays an equally important role;

- * communication in pedagogy - the active organization of the teacher's interaction on the basis of interaction with the students, the planned function of the implementation of a particular goal on the basis of the program performance;

- * communication is a multifaceted process of developing an individual's attitude, which arises from the need for cooperation activities is;

- * fear in students from incorrect pedagogical communication, insecurity in their own power arises, their attention, diligence movement slows down, speech dynamics breaks down, independent and free thinking ability decreases.

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